

Price Optimization using Sentiment Analysis and Random Forest Regression Algorithm

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Abstract— Sentiment analysis, also called the Opinion mining is a type of Natural Language Processing (NLP) in which the people's opinions, sentiments, emotions, attitudes etc. are extracted from the text based on the polarity. That is the positivity or negativity in the text. The sentiment analysis process involves various techniques like text preprocessing, feature extraction, machine learning, and deep learning. These techniques help in extracting useful information, from the text and categorizing it into different sentiment classes like positive, negative, or neutral. Random forest regression is a machine learning algorithm that can be used for price optimization based on sentiment analysis. This algorithm involves creating multiple decision trees and combining them to make a more accurate prediction. By analyzing customer sentiment and other factors, random forest regression can predict the optimal price for a product or service.

Keywords- Opinion mining, Polarity, Sentiments, Natural language processing.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is impossible to exaggerate the significance of user-generated evaluations given the growth of e-commerce and online platforms. These reviews offer insightful information about the caliber, effectiveness, and overall user experience of a good or service. However, the overwhelming number of reviews that are available online can make it difficult for users to gather useful data. By providing a quick and efficient way to determine the general perception of a good or service, sentiment analysis tools automatically analyze the sentiment of user reviews, thus aiding in resolving this issue. To modify their products in response to customer feedback, businesses can use this information, while consumers can use it to make informed purchases. Many sentiment analysis algorithms have been proposed to automate this analysis process. In this study, textual data are processed using the TextBlob Python library, which has a sentiment analysis module that employs machine learning techniques to categorize the sentiment of a given text. A pre-trained Nave Bayes classifier is used by

TextBlob's sentiment analysis module to categorize the given text's sentiment as either positive, negative, or neutral. The price is optimized on the basis of these sentiment values. Random forest regression algorithm can be used for price optimization

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sentiment analysis has become increasingly relevant in today's world with the rise of social media and online communication, as it allows businesses and individuals to gauge public opinion and make data-driven decisions. The random forest regression is a powerful machine learning algorithm that can be used for price optimization by analyzing multiple variables and identifying the optimal price point for a product.

In a study by, Sangeetha and Kumaran [1], the authors discuss the increasing popularity of online shopping and the importance of sentiment analysis in analyzing online reviews for improving customer satisfaction and predicting market outcomes. The article presents approach using a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN-LSTM) and support vector machine (SVM) classifier to perform sentiment analysis on customer reviews. The article concludes with a discussion of the challenges of sentiment analysis and the importance of neural language processing in this field.

In a study by Wankhade and Kulkarni [2], it provides a comprehensive overview of sentiment analysis. The authors begin by highlighting the growing popularity of sentiment analysis in recent years among researchers, businesses, governments, and organizations. They explain that sentiment analysis involves gathering and analyzing people's opinion, thoughts, and impressions on various products, subjects, and services. The article then discusses the different methods used in sentiment analysis, such as natural language processing and text mining, and explains how sentiment analysis is carried out at the document and sentence level.

Another study by Spedicato and Petrini [3], the authors used Random Forest algorithm for price optimization to improve sales performance. Random Forest Regression have also been applied to pricing optimization, specifically for regression problems. In this context a random forest model is trained to predict the optimal premium for prospective policyholders based on various input variables. The model can capture complex, nonlinear relationship between the input variables and optimal premium, which may be missed by a GLM. By utilizing the random forest model for pricing optimization, insurers can achieve more accurate and profitable pricing decisions.

A study by Fauzi et al. [4], the authors used sentiment analysis and price optimization to improve sales performance for an online grocery store. The authors used TextBlob and Naïve Bayes to perform sentiment analysis on customer reviews, and then used a pricing algorithm to determine the optimal prices for different products. The study found that adjusting prices based on sentiment analysis resulted in a 5.7% increase in revenue.

In another study by Hossain et al. [5], the authors used TextBlob and Naïve Bayes to analyze sentiment in Twitter data related to the 2020 US presidential election. According to the study, TextBlob's score had a 76.4% accuracy rate in detecting sentiment polarity compared to 86.8% for the Naive Bayes classifier. The study also discovered that the tone of tweets differed according to political affinities, with those from Joe Biden supporters generally being more upbeat than those from Donald Trump fans.

Overall, these literatures demonstrate the potential of sentiment analysis and price optimization to improve sales performance for e-commerce sites. TextBlob and Naïve Bayes are effective tools for sentiment analysis, and their results can be used to determine optimal pricing strategies. However, implementing sentiment-based pricing strategies requires careful considerations of customer preferences, product attributes, and market dynamics. By incorporating sentiment analysis into their pricing strategies, e-commerce sites can better understand customer preferences and make more informed decisions about their pricing strategies, ultimately improving sales performance.

III. MOTIVATION

Sentiment analysis is a powerful tool for e-commerce sites as it allows them to identify patterns in customer feedback that can inform product development, marketing strategies, and pricing decisions. Price optimization, on the other hand, is a technique that aims to maximize profits by adjusting prices based on market demand and other factors. By combining these two techniques, e-commerce sites can gain a better understanding of customer

sentiment and adjust their prices to better align with customer preferences.

The motivation for combining sentiment analysis with price optimization is to improve sales performance for e-commerce sites. By analyzing customer sentiment through their reviews, e-commerce sites can better understand their customer's preferences and adjust into their pricing algorithms, e-commerce sites can optimize their prices to improve revenue and profitability.

Overall, the motivation for using sentiment analysis with price optimization is to improve the customer experience on e-commerce sites, increase revenue, and stay competitive in a rapidly evolving market. By leveraging the power of sentiment analysis and price optimization, e-commerce sites can gain valuable insights into their customer's preferences and use that information to make more informed decisions about pricing and other aspects of their business.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for sentiment analysis with price optimization using TextBlob and Random Forest Regression algorithm involves the following steps:

A. Collect customer reviews: The first step in the methodology is to collect customer reviews from various sources, such as product pages, social media platforms, and review websites. These reviews will serve as the basis for sentiment analysis.

B. Preprocess the text data: Next, the data must be preprocessed to remove noise and irrelevant information. This involves tasks such as tokenization, stop word removal, and stemming.

C. Perform sentiment analysis: Once the text data has been preprocessed, sentiment analysis can be performed using TextBlob and Naïve Bayes. The TextBlob library provides a simple and efficient way to perform sentiment analysis on text data, while Naïve Bayes is a machine learning algorithm that can be used to classify text data into positive, negative or neutral categories.

D. Weights the ratings based on sentiment: After sentiment analysis, the next step is to weight the product reviews based on the sentiment scores of the corresponding reviews. Higher weights are assigned to more positive reviews, and lower weights are assigned to more negative reviews.

E. Determine optimal prices: Once the reviews have been weighted, the Random Forest regression algorithm can be used to determine the optimal prices for different products.

This algorithm takes various factors, such as positive and negative sentiment scores.

By following this methodology, e-commerce sites can use sentiment analysis with TextBlob and random forest regression to inform their pricing strategies and optimize their prices for maximum revenue and profitability.

V. BUILD MODEL

For building a reliable and accurate machine learning model for the successful prediction of price optimization we follow the following steps using TextBlob and Random Forest Regression.

Importing Libraries

```
from textblob import TextBlob
import numpy as np
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

TextBlob is used to process textual data. It offers a straightforward API for getting started with typical natural language processing (NLP) activities like part-of-speech tagging, noun phrase extraction, sentiment analysis, classification, translation, and others.

Matplotlib is a data visualization library for python. It provides a wide range of tools for creating static, animated, and interactive visualizations in python. It is useful creating line plots, scatter plots, bar plots and common chart types.

Random Forest Regressor is a machine learning model that belongs to the family of ensemble methods. It creates an ensemble of decision trees, where each tree is trained on a randomly sampled subset of the training data and a randomly sampled subset of the features.

NumPy is a widely-used Python library that is highly popular among scientists, data analysts and developers for performing scientific computing tasks and data analysis. This library provides efficient array operations and mathematical functions, making it an essential tool for numerical computing tasks.

Perform sentiment analysis

```
def review(request, id):
    if 'email' in request.session:
        user = request.session['email']
        product = Product.objects.get(id=id)
        if request.method == "POST":
            review = request.POST.get('message')
            rate = request.POST.get('rate')
            product = Product.objects.get(id=id)

            # Perform sentiment analysis
            blob = TextBlob(review)
            polarity_score = blob.sentiment.polarity
            subjectivity_score = blob.sentiment.subjectivity

            # Get the polarity score for each sentiment
            if polarity_score > 0:
                positive_score = polarity_score
                negative_score = 0
            elif polarity_score < 0:
                positive_score = 0
                negative_score = abs(polarity_score)
            else:
                positive_score = 0
                negative_score = 0

            # Save the review and rating to the database
            review = tbl_Review(user_id=user, product_id=product.id, review=review, rating=rate,
                                review.save())
```

```
for i in reviews:
    positive_avg += i.positive_score
    negative_avg += i.negative_score

# Calculate sentiment scores
if count > 0:
    positive_avg /= count
    negative_avg /= count

# Train a Random Forest Regressor model to predict the price optimization
X = np.array([positive_avg, negative_avg]).reshape(1, -1)
y = np.array([product.selling_price])
rfr = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=100, random_state=42)
rfr.fit(X, y)

# Predict the optimized price
optimized_price = rfr.predict([[positive_avg, negative_avg]])[0]
if positive_avg > negative_avg:
    optimized_price *= np.random.uniform(0.95, 0.99)
else:
    optimized_price *= np.random.uniform(1.01, 1.05)

# Update the optimised price of the price of the product
product.optimized_price = optimized_price
product.save()
```

```
def sentiment_graph(self, obj):
    avg_pos_score = obj.avg_pos_score
    avg_neg_score = obj.avg_neg_score
    avg_neu_score = obj.avg_neu_score

    # create a bar plot with positive and negative scores
    fig, ax = plt.subplots()
    ax.bar(['Positive', 'Negative', 'Neutral'], [avg_pos_score, avg_neg_score, avg_neu_score])
    # ax.hist([positive_score, negative_score], bins=10, color=['green', 'red'])
    # set the title and labels
    ax.set_title('Sentiment Analysis')
    ax.set_xlabel('Sentiment')
    ax.set_ylabel('Average Score')

    # save the plot to a buffer
    buffer = io.BytesIO()
    fig.savefig(buffer, format='png')
    buffer.seek(0)
```

VI.RESULT

In this study, product reviews from the users are collected and the data is processed. After processing the data, sentiment analysis is performed and the reviews are categorized based on the sentiment polarity score. Such as, Positive, Negative and Neutral. After performing the sentiment analysis, these Sentiment scores are used for training the random forest regression. From this algorithm, it predicts an optimal price.

Review	Rating	Positive Sentiment Score	Negative Sentiment Score	Neutral Sentiment Score
good	4.0	0.7	None	None
bad	1.0	None	-0.7	None
rtghyjkl	3.0	None	None	0.5
good	3.0	0.7	None	None
good	1.0	0.7	None	None

Original price *

Selling price *

Optimized price *

VII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, sentiment analysis with price optimization using TextBlob and Random Forest Regression is a powerful methodology that can help e-commerce sites improve their sales performance and profitability. By

analyzing customer sentiment through their reviews and weighting the reviews based on sentiment scores, e-commerce sites can gain a better understanding of their customers preferences and adjust their pricing strategies accordingly.

TextBlob and Naïve Bayes provide an efficient and accurate way to perform sentiment analysis on large volumes of text data, allowing e-commerce sites to quickly and easily identify patterns in customer feedback. By incorporating sentiment analysis into Random Forest Regression pricing algorithms, e-commerce sites can optimize their prices on market demand and customer preferences, resulting in increased revenue and profitability.

Overall, sentiment analysis with price optimization using TextBlob and Random Forest Regression gives a valuable technique that can help e-commerce sites stay competitive in a rapidly evolving market. By leveraging the power of sentiment analysis and price optimization, e-commerce sites can gain valuable insights into their customers' preferences and use that information to make more informed decisions about pricing and other aspects of their business.

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